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A Comparative Study of the Similarities Between the Music Album “*Red (Taylor’s Version)*” by Taylor Swift and the “*Bluets*” by Maggie Nelson Through a Symbolic Approach

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Abstract:

Songs serve as an effective medium for individuals to connect with their personal experiences, with lyrics playing a pivotal role in enabling emotional release and catharsis. The lyrics evoke memories, inspire reflection, and offer a sense of companionship, thus functioning as powerful tools for emotional expression. This research paper conducts a comparative analysis of Maggie Nelson’s *Bluets* and Taylor Swift’s music album *Red (Taylor’s Version)* through a symbolic lens. *Bluets*, composed of 240 prose-poetic fragments, blends memoir and lyrical essays to meditate on the color blue, reflecting on love, loss, and grief themes. In contrast, *Red (Taylor’s Version)*, released in 2021, revisits and expands upon Swift’s 2012 album *Red*, focusing on themes of love, personal growth, and heartbreak symbolized through the color red. Using a symbolic approach, this paper explores how color symbolism portrays the inner turmoil of the lyrical essayist and the songwriter. It also examines both works’ thematic depth and figurative writing styles, particularly the use of ambiguity. This study is supported by existing research associating colors metaphorically with emotional states.

Keywords: Depression, Color Symbolism, Grief, Lost Love, Personal Growth.

Exploring Symbolic Intersections in *Bluets* and *Red (Taylor’s Version)*

The Role of Color in Symbolic Expression

“Suppose I were to begin by saying that I had fallen in love with a colour. Suppose I were to speak this as though it were a confession; suppose I shredded my napkin as we spoke. It began slowly. An appreciation, an affinity. Then, one day, it became more serious” (Nelson 1).

Bluets starts with this opening line where Nelson introduces the idea of having an emotional attachment to a color, suggesting a significant attachment to color. This attachment implies her nervousness, as indicated by her shredding the napkin. It also implies how the connection with the color started with a growing sense of appreciation, how romantic feelings developed gradually, and how they intensified from casual to serious.

“And so I fell in love with a color– in this case, the color blue– as if falling under a spell, a spell I fought to stay under and get out from under, in turns” (Nelson 1). Nelson here introduces the color “blue” and almost has an enchanting emotional attachment as if falling under a spell and experiencing a push and pull force while fighting to stay under the spell and simultaneously removing herself from the hold it had.

On the other hand, Taylor Swift released a whole album on the color “red,” where she vividly portrays the color to describe the emotional experiences she had gone through in her few relationships. The color red symbolizes passion, love, danger, and anger, and she also leaves the exact nature of love open to interpretation. The song “Red,” named after the album itself, has few lyrics that directly imply the color and associate them with various emotions.

“Losing him was blue like I’d never known

Missing him was dark gray, all alone

Forgetting him was like trying to know

Somebody you never met

But loving him was red

Loving him was red” (“Red” 0:37-1:02).

This stanza is repeated thrice in the song, and she also adds the word “burning” before red to make the color appear more intense, emphasizing “burning red” thrice in the further lyrics. She uses colors to represent different emotional states of her heart and mind. Blue symbolizes deep sadness, dark grey symbolizes loneliness, and red represents intense passion and love. The adjective “burning” adds intensity to the color red and the pain associated with it, indicating that the passion of the relationship was both consuming and destructive. Similarly, she also uses color to describe the fleeting nature of beauty and the ending of the relationship, much like autumn leaves that are vibrant and full of green at their peak before they fall and shed their beauty, fading like how a person’s natural happiness fades after a beautiful relationship ends. “Colors in autumn, so bright, just before they lose it all” (“Red” 0:30-0:36).

While written in the aftermath of her relationship with a man she names “the prince of blue” and her close friend’s serious accident, *Bluets* considers the common associations of blue with sadness, loss, or periods of suffering (Watson). Nelson uses the color blue to reflect the nature of physical intimacy, expressing her hidden desire to be loved by “the prince of blue.” She shows the association with the color blue through various objects she uses. For instance, a blue junk (a wrapper with blue dye instructions), a navy-blue snake tattoo (On her prince of blue’s wrist), a speck of blue identified as a termite poison strip, blue bower, Yves Klein’s blue paintings, Lapis lazuli, a mountain of broken blue glass, bright blue pills (antidepressants), the square of blue paper, Robin-egg blue bathroom, collection of navy-blue bottle tops.

“Why blue? People ask me this question often. I never know how to respond. We don’t get to choose what or whom we love, I want to say” (Nelson 5). Nelson reflects on the unavoidable choice to select something of her own free will. She reflects on her attachment to blue, suggesting that love is not a conscious choice, whether for a person or a color. The blue color is very vividly associated with sadness and despair. This color holds strong symbolic interest, as she uses it in this context to raise psychological issues. Blue is a cold color associated with skin discoloration in cold weather, especially after death. Shakespeare uses this color as the color of truth when he writes, “Lie all manner of colors but blue.” It is considered that the color blue has unreal characteristics that describe depression without any reason. That is why, this color symbolizes of melancholy, sadness (I am blue, I feel blue, etc.) (Giguashvili 5). This, however, justifies Nelson’s mediation of the color blue.

Similarly, Taylor’s association with red is fitting, as red symbolizes love, anger, passion and danger. Red has many symbolic meanings: such as life, hope, courage, health, love, anger, vigor, heat, heated emotions, and optimism. For instance, the symbolic meaning of the phrase “red rose” is associated with the red color of blood. There is a saying, “Black Rose Is an Emblem of Love” (Giguashvili 5). To consider a few instances, Taylor has reflected on the color red in her song where she says, “Loving him was red” (“Red” 0:53-0:55), “Photo album on the counter, your cheeks were turning red” (“All Too Well” 1:51-1:55), signifying intense emotion. “Took off faster than a green light” (“Holy Ground” 0:19-0:21). Here, the green light can be seen as a contrast to red, signifying the end of something beautiful. “So you were never a saint”, and “I’ve loved in shades of wrong” (“State of Grace” 2:21-2:24), imply the shades of wrong with the color red. These lyrics reflect the intensity of the emotional turmoil.

In *Bluets*, Nelson describes blue as her companion in her loneliness and as both her solace and a reminder of isolation. “I have been trying, for some time now, to find dignity in my loneliness...Can blue solve the problem, or can it at least keep me company within it?”

(Nelson 28). Nelson also explores the existence of color only as a mere color by delving into the essence of it and symbolizing it with philosophical states. “I am trying to talk about what the blue means, or what it means to me, apart from meaning” (16). Nelson emphasizes that divinity can emerge from unexpected, and earthy experiences by intertwining the sacred and the profane. “But what if the prince of blue’s unbuttoned pants are the divine, I pleaded” (8)

Furthermore, it is noticeable that Nelson’s friend’s accident triggers a heightened awareness of the color blue, serving as a metaphor for the persistence of beauty amid traumas. “A friend had been in an accident. Perhaps she would not live...In the baby-shit yellow showers at my gym.....I noticed that the yellow paint was peeling in spots, and a decent, industrial blue was trying to creep in” (9). The blue of her friend’s trauma and the blue of her friend’s eyes become a striking symbol of life and hope, contrasting with her physical paralysis. “When I walked into my friend’s hospital room, her eyes were a piercing, pale blue and the only part of her body that could move. I was scared. So was she. The blue was beating” (9). Nelson always explains her points by first narrating the stories of people around her. She compares between how the blue color would help provide both hope and despair. She explains that she even tried to bring other colors into her life when she painted her apartment yellow but later repainted it blue, showing how deeply she was personally rooted in the color.

“Vincent van Gogh, whose depression, some say, was likely related to temporal lobe epilepsy...” (36) or “Standing in front of these blue paintings.... At the Tate....” (30). There are multiple excerpts where Nelson discusses the color blue philosophically to explain that even artists, philosophers and painters have associated the color blue as a symbol of emotional and existential struggle. “Goethe wrote Theory of Colours....” (10) or “Wittgenstein, who wrote his remarks on Colour....” (10) or “I am trying to talk about what blue means, or what it means to me, apart from meaning” (16). By exploring the philosophical insights from Goethe and Wittgenstein, Nelson explores the deeper meanings of blue beyond just aesthetics.

Exploring Thematic Resonance:

Blue’s function as an effect in Maggie Nelson’s *Bluets* is multifaceted as it proves to be both a source of anxiety and a soothing reassurance: the illness and the cure simultaneously (Golovchenko). As the major symbolism of blue paved the way for the other themes to develop throughout the text, blue gives rise to the associated pain and other themes like heartbreak, love, grief, loss, and personal growth. The thematic commonality is like Taylor’s *Red (Taylor’s Version)* album, as it also focuses on similar themes associating it with the color red.

“I have made efforts, however fitful, to live within other beads. During one particularly despondent New York City winter, I bought a huge can of bright yellow paint at the hardware store on Allen Street, imagining that I might buoy my soul with its cheer” (31-32). Nelson uses external changes to alleviate her heartbreak and pain, as buying yellow paint to cheer her soul, and she indicates personal growth by trying to do something to change. “I have been trying, for some time now, to find dignity in my loneliness....I have been finding this hard to do” (28). Nelson proves how hard she is trying to move on from a terrible heartbreak and that the lonely feeling made her struggle to find a sense of worth. Nelson also evokes a sense of spirituality amidst the feeling of heartbreak when she says, “Months before this afternoon I had a dream, and in this dream an angel came and said: You must spend more time thinking about the divine, and less time imagining unbuttoning the prince of blue’s pants at the Chelsea Hotel” (7).

“Above all, I want to stop missing you” (4), explains a raw admission of longing and the desire to move on to ease the broken heart’s pain and loss is immense. Nelson originally paved the way for the other themes to flow smoothly by letting the association with blue walk side by side. She mirrors the broader theme of loss when she mentions, “I never got any funding. My blues stayed local” (26). Besides all the gloominess, *Bluets* also shows glimpses of love and the realization of moving on from the pain, showing personal growth. Nelson truly shows the

absolute madness of falling so much in love that she even falls in love with the pain associated with it, particularly the color blue. “And so I fell in love with a colour— in this case, the colour blue— as if falling under a spell, a spell I fought to stay under and get out from under, in turns” (1), thus highlighting the consuming nature of love. Nelson also throws light on love’s involuntary, uncontrollable, and irresistible nature, which can sometimes be so powerful and unpredictable. “We don’t get to choose what or whom we love, I want to say. We just don’t get to choose” (5).

“If I were on my deathbed, I would name my love of the colour blue and making love with you as two of the sweetest sensations I knew on this earth” (87). The comparison of love to sensory experiences shows the consuming and enchanting nature. One of Nelson’s greatest signs is a deeper understanding and acceptance of introspection and loneliness, nailing more on personal growth. “It is easier, of course, to find dignity in one’s solitude. Loneliness is solitude with a problem” (28). Apart from love, personal growth, loss, and heartbreak, Nelson has also emotionally and beautifully portrayed grief when she says, “I wept until I aged myself. I watched this happen in the mirror” (34) or “I have felt myself becoming a servant of sadness. I am still looking for the beauty in that” (29) reflecting the pervasive nature of grief taking a visible toll on her and the ongoing struggle to find meaning and beauty in sorrow. Nelson also stresses the anxiety and the palpable fear of the intense emotional weight of grief on her reflecting, “I was scared. So was she. The blue was beating” (9).

Comparatively, Taylor portrays similar themes in her album. The signs of personal growth are visible when she repeatedly asserts her finality and determination of the decision to move on and break free from the cycle by saying, “We are never ever getting back together.” This song reflects on personal growth, realization, and moving on. “I’ve been loving you for quite some time” (“Stay, Stay, Stay” 1:00-1:02). This recurring phrase in the song reflects the decision to stay forever with the lover. The words from “State of Grace” like “Achilles Heel”

reflect that no matter how the bond is strong, there is always a weak point (her love more than the other person) that could lead to downfall, “mosaic broken hearts” and “armor falls” deals with pain, vulnerability and the process of healing. The state of a relationship going smoothly through ups and downs and then ending unexpectedly and suddenly is beautifully portrayed as “Loving him is like driving a new Maserati down a dead-end street/ Faster than the wind, passionate as sin, ending so suddenly” (“Red” 0:06-0:21).

The song “I Almost Do” focuses on pain of separation and the difficulty in moving on while still lingering on the attachment mentioned: “It takes everything in me, not to call you/ And I wish I could run to you/ And I hope you know that every time I don’t/ I almost do” (“I Almost Do” 2:57-3:15). In “Forever Winter,” the phrases “3 AM pacin” and “5 AM wasted” showcase anxiety, sleeplessness, alone with thoughts and “forever winter” versus “summer sun” contrasts underscoring the battle between darkness and a promise of better days. Even the title of the song, “Come Back, Be Here,” reflects the longing and difficulty of being part of it. The song “Better Man” discusses the importance of knowing one’s self-worth and moving on from loving someone who could not reciprocate healthily. It is mentioned as “Than lovin’ a man who didn’t know/ What he had when he had it” (“Better Man” 0:23-0:29) and “Than needing a man who could change his mind at any given minute” (“Better Man” 1:41-1:48). The repeated declaration of “the last time I’ll ever call you, babe” (“Babe” 1:01-1:05), shows her decision to move on. “All Too Well” is known as one of her best songs from this album as this song signifies the impact of loss and grief one faces and the difficulty one goes through to forget someone and stop themselves from loving them anymore with time described as paralyzing. “Time won’t fly, it’s like I’m paralyzed by it/ I’d like to be my old self again/ But I’m still trying to find it” (“All Too Well” 6:02-6:11). The phrase “All Too Well” itself highlights the aftermath of ending a relationship and the conflict with the inner self to move on while enduring the pain.

Figurative Language in Conveying Emotional Depth

Songwriters generally consider song lyrics a form of literary work and use figurative language to present more imaginative language that attracts the attention of music listeners. Listeners use song lyric to evoke emotions and understand the lyrics' meaning. They require an understanding of the state of the mind that can recognize the hidden meaning within the lyrics. Writers often convey these meanings through metaphor and other figurative language. Especially ambiguity. Authors commonly use figurative language as a form of expression in literary works. One literary work is song lyrics that resemble poetry. Descriptive words in figurative language have meanings that go beyond the literal meaning, namely using symbols to describe other things or events. Taylor Swift's songs are popularly known for the ambiguity of the language. This dissertation focuses on the ambiguity of the language used in Taylor's and Nelson's work.

In "*Red (Taylor's Version)*," the lyric "Feeling twenty-two" ("22" 0:44-0:45) is ambiguous because instead of referring to the age, it refers to the state of mind, implying a sense of mix emotions of freedom and recklessness that comes being in the early twenties. "Casually cruel in the name of being honest" ("All Too Well" 4:31-4:35) highlights she used the truth as a justification for hurtful behavior. "Thinking all love ever does is break and burn, and end" ("Begin Again" 1:15-1:20) reflects a past heartbreak. It leaves the question of whether this is a universal truth or a perception shaped by the writer's recent experiences. In one of the songs, "Better Man," there are a lot of instances where the ambiguity in the language is quite noticeable. "I just miss you, and I just wish you were a better man" ("Better Man" 1:03-1:08) captures both the frustration with the inability to change and longing for the person. "Sometimes, in the middle of the night, I can feel you again" ("Better Man" 0:57-1:02) reflects the remembrance of the emotional memories, and "I know the bravest thing I ever did was run"

(“Better Man” 0:57-0:56) reflects the acknowledgment of the difficulty of leaving a relationship.

The lyrics “This is falling in love in the cruelest way” (“Come Back....Be Here” 2:25-2:27) and “How strange that I don’t know you at all” (“Come Back....Be Here” 0:11-0:15) interpret that even though being deeply connected to someone, there is a realization at a certain point that people hardly know each other. When the loved one is far away, and the feeling of love is strong, the pain associated with it is intense, and the distance and situation become the cruelest thing. The lyric “I’d fall to pieces on the floor if you weren’t around” (“Forever Winter” 1:00-1:06) conveys a deep impact, suggesting vulnerability and ambiguity, suggesting a plea for the lover to stay. In “I Bet You Think About Me,” the repetition of the lyric title in the song creates an impact, suggesting both a taunt and hope, implying that the ex-lover might regret the separation. Another of Taylor’s famous songs, “I Know You Were Trouble,” uses “trouble” as a repeated metaphor for the ambiguous effect and realization of personal turmoil and the partner leaving her suddenly. The lyric “Blame is on me” (“I Know You Were Trouble” 0:38-0:40) indicates self-blame for getting involved in a relationship or for ignoring the red flags.

“Red,” a song based on the album title, is one of the songs with lots of ambiguity. A few instances of the lyrics are “Forgetting him was like trying to know somebody you never met” (“Red” 0:45-0:51) and “Memorizing him was as easy as knowing all the words to your old favorite song” (“Red” 1:15-1:21), suggesting the ambiguity of both evoking positive and negative emotions of familiarity and nostalgia and the difficulty in forgetting someone deeply loved and known. Again, in “State of Grace,” the title of the lyric itself can be interpreted in various ways, such as peace, divine blessing within the relationship, or a moment of perfection. The lyric “You break my heart in the blink of an eye” (“The Last Time” 1:25-1:27) showcases the suddenness of the pain and, at the same time, leaves open the reasons behind it. “Forever going with the flow/ But you’re friction” (“Traacherous” 1:41-1:45) gives a statement that is

open to interpretation as it compares the simplicity of following the hindering impact of resistance, indicating that the relationship is a natural progression and a cause of tension.

Comparatively, in *Bluets*, questioning the nature of love introduces ambiguity as it challenges the reader to consider multiple interpretations of emotional experiences. It is noticeable when Nelson mentions, “What kind of love is it, really? Don’t fool yourself and call it sublimity” (3). Later, she introduces a rhetorical question introducing doubt and difficulty focusing on the uncertain nature of love and relationships by saying, “Are you sure— one would like to ask— that it cannot love you back?” (15). Nelson also reflects on the ambiguity inherent in how individuals experience the world and how perception is subjective by mentioning, “Does the world look bluer from blue eyes? Probably not, but I choose to think so” (14). Apart from subjective perception, Nelson also indicates how people perceive colors, implying that they accept or reject a color’s existence in objects based on perspective, thus highlighting the ambiguity in interpreting sensory information. “You might as well act as if objects had the colors, the Encyclopedia says. -Well, it as you please. But what would it look like to act otherwise?” (19).

“Try, if you can, not to talk as if colors emanated from a single phenomenon. Keep in mind the effects of all the various surfaces, volumes, light-sources, films, expanses, degrees of solidity, solubility, temperature, elasticity, on color” (20). Nelson encourages a broader understanding of color as a difficult interaction of various factors instead of considering it a singular phenomenon, highlighting the ambiguous nature of language and perception. Nelson also compares the perception of color with the experience of love and points out the uncertainty in assigning inherent qualities to both color perception and love by likening them to each other. “We mainly suppose the experiential quality to be an intrinsic quality of the physical object. Perhaps it is also that of love” (20-21). “Does an album of written thoughts perform a similar displacement of the ‘original’ thoughts themselves? (Please don’t start protesting here that there

are no thoughts outside of language, which is like telling someone that her colored dreams are, in fact, colorless.)” (77-78). In this excerpt, Nelson questions the relationship between thoughts and their written representations, focusing on how language captures and possibly distorts original ideas.

Conclusion

This comparative study highlights how Maggie Nelson’s *Bluets* and Taylor Swift’s *Red (Taylor’s Version)* use color as a powerful emotional and symbolic tool. Nelson’s blue and Swift’s red become metaphors for love, grief, longing, and personal growth. Both artists employ figurative language and ambiguity to deepen emotional resonance, using color not just descriptively but as central to their narratives. Their works mirror a shared journey from heartbreak to healing, blending personal expression with universal themes, ultimately bridging the gap between the individual and the collective through symbolic depth.

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